

NFDI-MatWerk

Short Guide on Research Data Management Plans

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Research Data Essentials
and Solutions

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Fundamental Principles of Research Data Management (RDM)

Data lifecycle throughout scientific project's duration

Make your research data FAIR

Findable

F Describe your research data with meaningful metadata available in a searchable database and reference it using a Persistent Identifier (PID).

Accessible

A Ensure that access to data and metadata is technically possible and define the authentication and authorization process that is necessary.

Interoperable

I Use established standards for the formats of your research data and for the metadata and metadata vocabularies.

Re-useable

R The metadata for your research data is detailed, domain-specific, and machine-readable. Make it clear how your data was created and under which conditions it can be re-used

What is a data management plan good for?

A data management plan (DMP) structures the handling of research data in a scientific project. It describes how to deal with the data used during and after the end of the project. Many third-party funding bodies (DFG, Horizon Europe, etc.) expect information on the handling of research data as part of a funding application when awarding funds from certain funding lines. A formal DMP is only required in the rarest of cases, especially by the EU. Nevertheless, a DMP is beneficial for the work on a research project. In particular, a DMP allows the current project status and its specifics to be noted throughout the entire research data lifecycle. Thus it is helpful for the administration and to keep the overview.

- Storage: server, cloud...
- Redundancy and backup
- Data security
- Version control
- Data organization

Key aspects of DMP

- Data description
- Documentation and data quality
- Storage, Archiving
- Exchange, Accessibility
- Legal obligations
- Responsibilities

Make your data work for you

Type	Experimental data
Source	MTS 810
Format	csv, log
Quantity	< 1 GB

Free DMP-Tools

- [RDMO](#) (DE)
- [ARGOS](#) (EU)
- [DMP-online](#) (EU)
- [DMPtool](#) (US)

Data Description, Documentation and Quality

Data Types

- Documents, spreadsheets, protocols
- Methodologies and workflows, standard operating procedures
- Lab notebooks, transcripts, codebooks, audio- and videotapes
- Photographs, films, test responses
- Slides, artefacts, specimens
- Data files, models, algorithm

Data description entails providing a clear and comprehensive overview of the data used in the study. This includes specifying the type of data, its sources, and the methods employed for data acquisition. Researchers need to elucidate the variables, measurements, and units used to record and quantify the data. Proper documentation of the data's characteristics and structure ensures transparency, enabling other researchers to understand, interpret, and reproduce the study's findings.

Data Sources

Research data can be extracted from a wide variety of places, depending on the specific research question and methodology. It could be generated within the research project or mined from external databases and re-used. The typical sources of the data in materials science research are:

- **Research instruments:** it is advisable to include essential details such as the instrument type, model/vendor, configuration, calibration procedure, acquisition mode, analysis workflow, and, if applicable, the detectors used.
- **Computations and simulations:** it is recommended to specify the software used including the information on version and provide documentation needed to validate the data and facilitate its re-use.
- **External data sources:** researchers can access publicly available datasets or data repositories that house data collected by other researchers or organizations.

Data Formats (Source: [MPDL](#))

Data type	Recommended	Non-recommended
Text	TXT, HTML, RTF, PDF/A	DOC, PPT
Tabular	CSV, TSV, SPSS portable	XLS
Images	TIFF, JPEG2000, PNG	GIF, JPG
Multimedia	Container: AVI, WAV, MP4, Ogg Codec: Theora, Dirac, FLAC	Windows Media Video, QuickTime, H264
Structured	XML, RDF, JSON	RDBMS

Preservation: Storage, Archiving and Security

Properly managing data storage and archiving ensures the security, accessibility, and long-term preservation of research data, facilitating reproducibility and future use. Digital research data is stored on a variety of media and in a variety of locations. However, both storage medium and storage location have different strengths and weaknesses. Depending on the medium, there are serious differences in terms of lifespan, compatibility and resistance to environmental influences. The key considerations for storage and technical archiving of research data are:

Lifetime of storage media

Hard drive:
2-10 years

USB-Sticks:
10-30 years

DVD:
< 30 years

- Choose **appropriate storage** solutions based on the volume, type, and sensitivity of the data. Options may include local servers, cloud-based storage, external hard drives, or data repositories.
- **Redundancy and Backup:** Implement redundant storage and backup strategies to safeguard against data loss.
- **Data Security:** Ensure data security through encryption, access controls, and authentication mechanisms to protect sensitive information.
- **Version Control:** Establish version control mechanisms to track changes and revisions made to the data over time, enabling researchers to revert to previous states if needed.
- **Data Organization:** Organize data in a systematic and standardized manner, employing appropriate file naming conventions and folder structures for easy retrieval and management

Useful Tools

 [Coscine](#)

 [Kadi4mat](#)

Sharing & Reuse: Data exchange and long-term Accessibility

To ensure the beneficial utilization of research data by third parties, a systematic and criterion-based selection process is essential. This selection process necessitates the permanent archiving and accessibility of the data using appropriate hardware or software infrastructure. Moreover, clear communication channels must be established to facilitate data exchange. Considering the rapidly advancing technical developments, it becomes imperative to remain adaptable as these advancements occur at increasingly shorter intervals. The data's permanent accessibility implies that it should be available to a specific group of recipients through common search engines without any time restrictions.

Is your data prepared for sharing?

- The legal aspects of the data is clarified
- The data is available in a common format
- The data is reliable
- The data is citable by persistent identifiers (PIDs)
- The data is described with extensive **metadata**↓

Bibliographic or administrative data contains information on the management of the data, the origin of the entirety of the data, and is more general

Content descriptive or technical data describe individual aspects of data sets in more detail. Many subjects already have their own metadata standards (e.g. matportal).

Make your data findable

Persistent Identifier (PID)

Publications and data can be given a unique, permanent designation - a so-called Persistent Identifier (PID). This guarantees permanent accessibility. An internationally widely used system for this purpose is the Digital Object Identifier (DOI).

ORCID

Multiple names, different spellings or a change of name can mean that researchers cannot be clearly assigned. This is where a PID for researchers comes in handy - ORCID. ORCID provides a permanent digital identifier that distinguishes you from all other researchers - like a fingerprint. It can be integrated into important research processes such as manuscript and proposal submission.

Data becomes traceable and reusable for others

Interdisciplinary research is supported

Recognition for own research

Legal obligations, Responsibilities and resources

Legal obligations and framework conditions (rights of use and copyright as well as rights to third-party intellectual property and patent law) must already be checked in advance of the project and briefly named in the application. The legal obligations apply across the board to the recording, documentation, storage, archiving and subsequent use of the data collected or used. This applies in particular to coordinated programs in which data (codes, experimental data or similar) are further processed. If the project is based on already existing data, it must be considered whether the consent for use by the originator of the data is necessary and has been given [[Source – DFG](#)].

Hard drive: ownership

Data: ownership

Software: licenses

Database: copyrights

Copyright law (Deutsch UrhG) protects certain intellectual creations and performances. In the case of intellectual creations, the focus of protection is on the work as a whole and, in the case of intellectual performances, on the performance process. A database is a good example: if many works are gathered together, there is often no new creation (lack of creation level). There is no new intellectual property right on one of the works, but possibly on the performance of the compilation.

A **data license** refers to a legal agreement or contract that governs the terms and conditions under which data can be accessed, used, shared, or redistributed. It outlines the rights and permissions granted by the data owner or provider

Useful license choosers:

[CC license chooser](#)

[Choose a license](#)

Useful Tools and Techniques

*Electronic Lab Notebook

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